

Table S9: Comparison of the range of inter and interspecific uncorrected p-distances (%) among *Teretrurus* species, for three mitochondrial genes. Values in parentheses indicate the number of pairwise comparisons.

Species Pairs		P-distance		
Species 1	Species 2	16S	12S	ND4
<i>T. sanguineus</i> (2)	NA	NA	0	NA
<i>T. rhodogaster</i> (6)	NA	0 (6)	0 (6)	0–0.3 (6)
<i>T. hewstoni</i>	NA	0–0.4 (28)	0–1.6 (28)	0–1.6 (28)
<i>T. travancoricus</i>	NA	0 (6)	0 (6)	0 (6)
<i>T. rhodogaster</i>	<i>T. hewstoni</i>	4.1–4.4 (32)	4.5–7.2 (32)	14.6–15.3 (32)
<i>T. sanguineus</i>	<i>T. hewstoni</i>	3.2–3.5 (8)	5.0–5.3 (12)	12.9–13.1 (8)
<i>T. travancoricus</i>	<i>T. hewstoni</i>	4.7–5.0 (32)	6.1–6.5 (32)	16.7 – 17.4 (32)
<i>T. agumbensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. hewstoni</i>	0.8–1.1 (8)	2.3–3.5 (8)	8.1 – 8.9 (8)
<i>T. albiventer sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. hewstoni</i>	4.9–5.2 (24)	5.6–6.2 (24)	16.2–16.9 (24)
<i>T. periyarensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. hewstoni</i>	4.3–4.6 (8)	4.2–5.4 (8)	13.4–13.9 (8)
<i>T. siruvaniensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. hewstoni</i>	1.0–1.5 (16)	1.8–2.8 (16)	7.5–8.3 (16)
<i>T. sanguineus</i>	<i>T. rhodogaster</i>	3.2–3.3 (4)	4.0–5.6 (8)	11.5–11.8 (4)
<i>T. travancoricus</i>	<i>T. rhodogaster</i>	4.7–4.8 (16)	7.4–8.3 (16)	15.4–15.8 (16)
<i>T. agumbensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. rhodogaster</i>	4.1–4.2 (4)	6.1–7.4 (4)	18.6–18.9 (4)
<i>T. albiventer sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. rhodogaster</i>	4.5–4.6 (12)	7.7–8.3 (12)	16.9–17.2 (12)
<i>T. periyarensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. rhodogaster</i>	2.8 (4)	5.1–6.8 (4)	12.3–12.5 (4)
<i>T. siruvaniensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. rhodogaster</i>	3.9–4.1 (8)	5.3–6.8 (8)	16.6–17.2 (8)
<i>T. travancoricus</i>	<i>T. sanguineus</i>	6.0–6.1 (4)	6.6–6.7 (8)	14.8 (4)
<i>T. agumbensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. sanguineus</i>	3.0 (1)	4.9–5.0 (2)	15.2 (1)
<i>T. albiventer sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. sanguineus</i>	6.1 (3)	6.6–6.7 (6)	14.5 (3)
<i>T. periyarensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. sanguineus</i>	1.9 (1)	2.2 (2)	6.6 (1)

<i>T. siruvaniensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. sanguineus</i>	2.6–2.8 (2)	4.8 (2)	15.3–15.9 (2)
<i>T. agumbensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. travancoricus</i>	5.1–5.2 (4)	6.1 (4)	17.2–17.3 (4)
<i>T. albiventer sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. travancoricus</i>	1.1 (12)	1.1 (12)	3.8–4.0 (12)
<i>T. periyarensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. travancoricus</i>	5.4 (4)	7.1 (4)	14.7 (4)
<i>T. siruvaniensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. travancoricus</i>	5.4–5.6 (8)	4.8–5.8 (8)	18.2 – 18.8 (8)
<i>T. albiventer sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. agumbensis sp. nov.</i>	5.4 (3)	5.8 (3)	17.2 (3)
<i>T. siruvaniensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. agumbensis sp. nov.</i>	0.2–0.4 (2)	1.7–1.8 (2)	5.6–5.9 (2)
<i>T. periyarensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. albiventer sp. nov.</i>	5.4 (3)	6.7–6.8 (3)	14.9 (3)
<i>T. siruvaniensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. albiventer sp. nov.</i>	5.1–5.4 (6)	3.9–5.0 (6)	17.9–18.2 (6)
<i>T. siruvaniensis sp. nov.</i>	<i>T. periyarensis sp. nov.</i>	3.6–3.9 (2)	5.8–5.9 (2)	15.9–16.3 (2)